
TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP AND TEACHER PERFORMANCE: A DESCRIPTIVE CORRELATIONAL STUDY

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Abstract:

This study investigates the relationship between transformational leadership practices of school principals and teacher performance in the Compostela West District, Davao de Oro, Philippines. It aims to fill the research gap regarding how principals' leadership styles influence teacher performance, particularly focusing on the dimensions of vision building, individualized consideration, intellectual stimulation, and innovative climate. A quantitative research design, specifically a cross-sectional, descriptive, and innovative correlational survey, was employed. The respondents comprised 200 elementary and secondary teachers from thirteen schools within the district. Data was collected using modified questionnaires. The results indicate that principals in Compostela West District exhibit a high level of transformational leadership across all four dimensions. Teachers rated their principals' transformational leadership in vision building, individualized consideration, intellectual stimulation, and innovative climate consistently high. Teachers' performance, as measured by their IPCR-F scores, was also rated very satisfactory, indicating effective and efficient delivery of their professional duties. No significant differences were found in the perceived transformational leadership skills of principals when grouped by teachers' sex and age. Furthermore, the correlation analysis revealed a positive relationship between transformational leadership and teacher performance. These findings underscore the importance of transformational leadership in fostering a positive school environment, though they also highlight the need to explore additional factors that may impact teacher performance. Recommendation include sustaining and enhancing transformational leadership practices through professional development, collaborative school activities, and further research to explore the multifaceted nature of teaching performance and leadership dynamics.

Keywords: transformational leadership, teacher performance, educational leadership, principal leadership, descriptive-correlational study

1. Introduction

Teachers are vital in the educational system as the central component for achieving a school's vision, mission, and objectives. Their performance is crucial, as it directly influences the caliber of education the learners receive. Essentially, the quality of educators in a country directly impacts the total level of education. As educators, they transmit knowledge and shape the next generation's character, critical thinking skills, and future opportunities. Consequently, by prioritizing and consistently evaluating teachers' performance, educational institutions may effectively accomplish their academic goals and provide students with the necessary skills to thrive in a constantly changing world.

However, it has been observed in Turkey that teachers' performance tends to decline as the degree of schooling advances (Ozgenel & Mert, 2019). This presents a predicament: as the degree of schooling advances, the objectives of schools grow increasingly complex, requiring teachers at higher school levels to perform at a higher level than their colleagues at lower school levels. This suggests that higher levels of education may present challenges or factors that can impact teachers' efficiency or perceived competence, in contrast to lesser levels. This finding may have ramifications for educational policies and practices aimed at maintaining or improving teacher effectiveness across all levels of schooling.

Based on a 2018 report from the World Bank Group, teachers in Mindanao receive little to no rewards for their exceptional performance, which decreases their motivation to improve. As a result, there is a noticeable pattern in which teachers place greater importance on being on time rather than focusing on effective teaching and student learning (Molina et al., 2018). According to statistics, 70% of teachers and 50% of principals consider timeliness a top priority, whereas just 20% of instructors and 14% of principals emphasize student learning. In Mindanao, the emphasis is generally placed on efficiency and timeliness rather than quality education outcomes when determining efficacy. However, instructors in Sarangani Province need help with various problems, including limited access to individualized learning resources, absenteeism and language barriers. Despite these challenges, teachers typically consider themselves effective in the classroom (Isao, 2021; Lariosa et al., 2022; Brillantes & Nebria, 2021). Consequently, it is essential to investigate how school administrators' leadership styles impact teachers' actual performance to improve the overall quality of teaching.

Having worked as an educator in public schools for 16 years, I have had the opportunity to engage with many principals, each of whom has brought distinct traits to the table and demonstrated various leadership methods. The first, a 60-year-old man, remains composed despite challenges, creating an environment where every problem has a solution. The second, a 55-year-old woman, fosters initiative and encourages risk-taking. An older woman emphasizes a steady pace over deadlines, ensuring thoroughness. A middle-aged man relies heavily on teachers and does not foster independence, while a young male principal, competitive and a perfectionist, supports holistic development beyond academics. Another middle-aged man builds strong stakeholder connections and balances academics with extracurriculars. Despite struggling with trust, a meticulous middle-aged woman has overseen school and student discipline improvements. This varied leadership style uniquely contributes to the school's atmosphere and student development, providing a rich foundation for understanding transformational leadership in educational settings.

Although the importance of teachers in school effectiveness is acknowledged, more research is needed on how the transformational leadership of school administrators affects teachers' performance. Additionally, a research gap exists in understanding the moderating effect of

principal leadership experience and teachers' professional development in the relationship between transformational leadership and teachers' performance. Thus, this research aims to address these research gaps to provide a more holistic understanding of the interplay between leadership and teacher performance, thereby offering valuable insights for educational policymakers to improve the overall quality of education.

2. Literature Review

Teachers' performance has always been an interesting research area in terms of teacher quality and improving student outcomes. On the other hand, transformational leadership, principal leadership experience, and teachers' professional development are interesting variables to consider when studying teachers' performance. More so, the putative relationship of these variables is an interesting literature quest. As such, this chapter presents the review of available literature on transformational leadership, teachers' performance, and their relationship. Also, this literature attempts to provide related literature on moderating variables such as principal leadership experience and teachers' professional development.

Transformational Leadership. Transformational leadership in education is defined by the presence of charismatic leaders who effectively inspire and motivate teachers to strive towards common goals and objectives collaboratively. These leaders possess a persuasive and captivating vision for enhancing and advancing the school, instilling a strong feeling of purpose and dedication among the instructors. They create transparent communication channels, actively engage stakeholders in the decision-making process, and cultivate a creative school culture that promotes innovation. This leadership style prioritizes proactive problem-solving and fosters the collaborative creation of objectives, resulting in a cohesive and coordinated approach. It is highly efficient in meeting the changing requirements of students and the wider community, fostering a strong feeling of inclusion and dedication among all parties involved.

Transformational leadership has been extensively studied and researched throughout the years, leading to several variations. Burns' 1978 theory of transformational leadership established the fundamental idea of this leadership style. Burns (1978) posited that transformative leadership is fundamentally rooted in the leader's interpersonal relationships, patterns, and values. Therefore, leadership involves having power or authority to influence others and examining the ethical principles of leaders to inspire their followers to develop their own sense of moral duty and motivation to contribute towards achieving the organization's goals (Amelia et al., 2024).

Bass (2020) expounded the idea of Burns (1978) about transformational leadership. Bass expressed that transformational leadership also benefited employees of the organization as it helps increase their job satisfaction, primarily by recognizing their positive contributions towards achieving organizational targets, fostering a sense of fulfillment and motivation. This satisfaction can be argued to stem from knowing that they were able to positively contribute to the attainment of organizational goals. Additionally, the ethical dimension of transformational leadership (Bass and Steidlmeier 1999) ,underscores the importance of integrity and authenticity in leadership further contributing to a positive work environment and employee morale.

Bartolome et al (2017) became more specific in discussing the four dimensions of transformational leadership. Leithwood (2021) explained that transformational leadership has the following components: build the vision and goals of the school, provides intellectual stimulation, offer support individually, be exemplary to the important values of the organization, indicating high work performance, build creative school culture and developing structures and encourage involvement in the decision-making process.

In a more recent study of Slocum and Hellriegel (2020), transformational leaderships were reduced into four. The dimension is made up of an attitude that shows consideration of individual-based, build intellectual stimulation, stimulate motivation and nurture an ideal influence among his followers, or in this context among teachers (Slocum & Hellriegel, 2020). Nevertheless, Slocum & Hellriegel's (2020) concept of transformational leadership is still very similar to Bass

(1985) that involves school leaders exemplifying morality, commitment and behaviors to model and motivate the organization's members to innovate and create solutions to problems both in school and in community.

Creating solutions to address problems either in school or community requires a certain degree of creativity and demands determination to the constraints based on organizational contexts. Abdullah, et al. (2016) argued that since transformational leaders need to establish close relationship with teachers and help them build creative work at the workplace, manage autonomy, promote innovations and creativity, principals' transformational leadership is closely connected with teachers' creativity which can be extended to their performance of duty and could translate to improved performance. Indirectly, it can be argued that principals' transformational leadership is related with the teachers' performance metrics.

When teachers are committed to their profession and to their job, the likelihood of increasing job satisfaction and performance becomes higher. Interestingly Kareem, et.al (2023) claimed that transformational leadership positively impacts teachers' commitment to their institution, to student development and self-development. This is so transformational school leaders play an important role in promoting educational innovation and restructuring by creating a vision for the future, building a culture of collaboration, and empowering others to become leaders themselves. However, what Kareem, et.al (2023) were not able to establish is whether and how transformational leadership translate these commitments into actual performance.

The theory of transformational leadership is not perfect and free of criticism (Buaniyan & McWilliams, 2018). For example, transformational leadership effectiveness can be greatly hindered when educational leaders do not prioritize multiculturalism and equity. Berkovich (2016) underscores the importance of transformational leadership in a multicultural context because it accommodates diverse perspectives for identifying needs and issues in various school environments. However, as argued by Lewis, Boston and Peterson (2017), a lack of cultural awareness and comprehension presents obstacles to implementing meaningful change. Without a grasp of different viewpoints, cultures and backgrounds, bridging conflicts between groups, which is the initial step in transformational leadership, becomes challenging (Lewis, Boston & Peterson, 2017). Hence, it becomes evident that culture should play a fundamental role in shaping the school's collective vision and motivating leaders to exhibit positive behaviors in their pursuit of equity.

Scholars may have their criticisms of transformational leadership theory, but these critiques should not undermine its value and effectiveness. Instead, the limitations of this theory should be seen as opportunities to incorporate other leadership theories to enhance the utility of transformational leadership. In the future, there is potential to refine transformational leadership, adding more structure to it while maintaining its adaptability. This approach can open possibilities for involving stakeholders with diverse objectives in school improvement efforts and adopting a multifaceted strategy for bringing about change in the educational systems (Buaniyan & McWilliams, 2018).

Hence, the main research endeavor in educational transformational leadership is understanding how this leadership style's impact on teachers and students can be translated into actual improvements in performance and educational outcomes. We need to figure out if and how transformational leadership leads to concrete results.

In Indonesia, teachers were observed to be lacking in terms of subject knowledge and teaching skills hence affecting their overall performance as teachers (Rosser and Fahmi, 2018). Low quality of teachers identified as one factors why Indonesia performed poorly, under in the 10th lowest category, in the Program for International Assessment (PISA) survey in 2018 (Kanya et.al, 2021). Hence, it is a high time to investigate factors that affects the poor performance of teacher in International scale.

Additionally, the importance of cultural awareness and equity in diverse educational settings is emphasized and how transformational leadership addresses issues related to different cultures

and promotes fairness. Bridging the gap between cultural perspectives and backgrounds to create positive change in schools is a complex challenge that needs more investigation. It is also interesting to explore in educational transformational leadership on finding out how commitments and positive effects on stakeholders lead to better performance and educational outcomes. It's also important to understand the role of cultural awareness and equity in the effectiveness of transformational leadership in different educational contexts.

Teachers' Performance. In the Department of Education, performance of teachers are gauged based on their instructional practices in the RPMS toolkit as key result area or KRA. To wit, these are (i) content knowledge and pedagogy, (ii) diversity of learners & assessment and reporting, (iii) curriculum planning and (iv) community linkages and professional engagement & personal growth and professional development (DepEd, 2020).

Instructional practices are techniques that teachers use to help students become independent and strategic learners. These strategies become learning strategies when students select the ones and use them to accomplish tasks or meet goals. In other words, instructional practices are about ongoing interaction between teachers and their students through the elements of teaching and learning (Francisco & Celon, 2020).

Investigating the teachers' instructional practices and students' achievement, Francisco & Celon (2020) claimed that teachers face the challenges of conducting active engagement to their teachers through proper mentoring and coaching. They are also challenged to maintain to maintain good relationship with their students and their parents, finding support to improve their teaching practices and intensifying faculty development program to improve competencies.

Pedagogical Content Knowledge has been defined as "the body of understanding, knowledge, skills, and dispositions that a teacher needs to perform effectively in a given teaching situation" (Grieser & Hendricks, 2018). Most scholars' conceptualize PCK are composed of four common components: (a) knowledge of students' understanding, (b) instructional strategies and representations, (c) curriculum, and (d) the teacher's values and beliefs about education. However, in the study involving teachers teaching research, origins of their orientations to teaching their content include there: (i) own experiences of learning/being taught research methods; (ii) methodological experience; (iii) formal training; (iv) early experiences with teaching; and (v) pedagogical beliefs and values (Nind, 2020).

The pedagogical 'knowledge base' of teachers includes all the required cognitive knowledge for creating effective teaching and learning environments. The pedagogical knowledge of teacher has the following components: knowledge of classroom management, knowledge of teaching methods, knowledge of classroom assessment, structure and adaptivity, knowledge of individual student characteristics and knowledge of learning processes (Voss, Kunter, & Baumert, 2011).

Knowledge of Diverse Learners (KDL) is increasingly recognized as an essential component of knowledge base for effective teaching as in today's schools, teachers must be prepared to teach a diverse population of students. Hence, teachers need to be aware that their students in a classroom are and always have been different from one another in a variety of ways. Knowledge of Diverse Learners refers to an understanding of diversity of students in terms of their abilities and interests and how they respond to diverse situations; an application of different teaching strategies; and how various types of classroom activities might be managed (Rahman, Scaife, Yahja, & Jalil, 2010).

Thinking of the children at all levels of ability is significantly influenced by the type of opportunities they are given. Offering the learners the right chances to develop their cognitive and creative potential should be a priority in the design curricula. To foster innovative teaching, curricula need to undergo a skillful and thorough development, where teachers can adopt different innovative teaching strategies according to the diverse needs of the students (Naz & Murad, 2017).

One of the ways to address student diversity is to provide diversified experiences in the class. Literatures argue that diverse experiences can enhance students' learning, and positively affect critical thinking skill which is "one of the most important aims of education". More so, students' sensitivity and awareness of self can be developed through diverse experiences.

Classroom diversity has positive, educational effects on student learning. Given that the students' diversity can make an important contribution to their effective learning, critical academic skills, and ultimately critical thinking, the teachers need to adopt many strategies of valuing diversity to enhance their learning (Wu, Tu, Wu, Le, & Reynolds, 2012).

Classroom assessment is an essential component of the teaching-learning process. Thus, improving the assessment skills of the teachers in English should be prioritized. School administrators and officials should realize that improving educational standards includes quality classroom practices of which classroom assessment is of crucial aspect (Lasaten, 2016). The development of critical thinking skills requires the development of an effective classroom assessment that is purposely chosen to target the development of certain skills (Baylon, 2014).

Teacher's knowledge on assessment is also significant for teachers to deliver quality instruction. Her orientation on classroom assessment allows her to develop questioning techniques that facilitate learning. Teacher's questioning has long been employed as an instructional technique. In fact, teacher assessment competences resulted in variability in teacher questioning practices, which further impacted student learning. More so, teacher assessment literacy was dynamics situated in context. It interrelated with other mediating factors at the personal, institutional, and socio-cultural levels (Jiang, 2020).

In an inclusive classroom, teachers' training on differentiated assessment for differentiated learning approach is necessary to equip teachers with the required knowledge and skills especially those who are not specialists. In the study involving specialist teachers and non-specialists, the specialists know and can apply most of them in assessing persons with special needs in inclusive setting while the non-specialists neither know nor able to apply them in assessing the special population in all-inclusive classroom (Idika & Eke, 2017). The importance of assessment cannot be over emphasized. In an inclusive setting, it is imperative to introduce differential assessment mode. Teachers should play significant roles in using differential methods for this special population for both formative and summative assessments.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the Department of Education releases the DepEd Order 31, s. 2020 outlining the interim guidelines for assessment and grading in light of the basic education learning continuity plan. The policy is grounded on the following principles: (i) assessment should be holistic and authentic capturing the attainment of the most essential learning competencies; (ii) assessment is the integral for understanding student learning and development, (iii) a variety of assessment strategies is necessary, with formative assessment taking priority to inform teaching and promote growth and mastery; (iv) assessment and feedback should be a shared responsibility among teachers, learners and their families; and (v) assessment and grading should have a positive impact on learning.

In the Department of Education, curriculum and planning as key results area (KRA) in the resource – based performance management system includes selecting, developing organizing and using appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals and setting achievable and appropriate learning outcomes that are aligned with learning competencies (DepEd, 2020). Hence, alignment of the learning targets, teaching-learning experiences and assessment strategy is of paramount importance. When designing a learning experience, course or program, it is important that there is a good fit between the learning outcomes, assessments, and teaching and learning activities; in other words, that the three components are aligned (Biggs & Tang, 2011). This helps ensure teaching and learning activities enable students to develop the knowledge and skills in the learning outcomes an prepare for formal assessments. In turn, assessments that align with the outcomes and planned learning activities help teachers and students determine whether, and to what extent, the outcomes have been achieved.

Interestingly, Urbano (2020) explored the instructional practices of teachers in public schools in the Division of Nueva Vizcaya. He found out that the instructions employed by the teachers were aligned with the learning competencies. In fact, it was evident that teachers used learning resources that were issued by the government through DepEd and other non-government

bodies or individuals while practicing teachers practiced the integration of information, communications and technology (ICT) materials in teaching the lessons. However, teachers fell short of the required time in implementing learning competencies of the K to 12 Mathematics 10 curriculum guide due to disruptions of classes, although interventions were done to address the issues. Yet, most of the instruction and summative assessment employed and administered by the teachers were aligned with the learning competencies (Urbano, 2020).

When it comes to choosing the teaching methods, teaching methods are patterns of teacher behavior that occur either simultaneously or in sequence in a verified way. However, it is interesting to note that the teaching methods used by the teachers determine the performance of their students. In particular, discussion and demonstration teaching methods greatly improve the students' academic performance than the lecture method which was passive, and teacher centered (Isa, Mammam, Badar, & Bala, 2020).

In the side of the coin, Ganyaupfu (2013) argued that to facilitate the process of knowledge transmission, teachers should apply to appropriate teaching methods that best suit specific objectives and level exit outcomes. Hence, he further argued that as learning is a process that involve investigating, formulating, reasoning and using appropriate strategies to solve problems, teachers should realize that it becomes more effective if the students are tasked to perform rather than asked to remember some information. A typical learning environment with a presentation from the course teacher accompanied by a lecture neither promotes learners' participation nor builds the required level of reasoning among students (Ganyaupfu,2013).

Truly, the effectiveness of these teaching and learning processes largely depends on the choice of the teacher's teaching method. As a matter of fact, the teaching method had both a positive and negative influence on student's performance. Hence, regular in service training for teachers as it is believed that in service training addresses contemporary issues that will help teachers understand various methodologies and how to incorporate them in their day to day teaching (Atandi, Billiah, & Jared, 2019).

In Department of Education, community linkages and professional engagement and personal growth and professional development as key results area includes building relationships with parents/guardians and the wider school community to facilitate involvement in the educative process and participated in professional networks to share knowledge and enhance practice.

Good relationships between the parents and the school are associated with positive outcomes in school. In particular, increased parent educational involvement is associated with regular school attendance, higher academic performance, higher standardized test scores, improved behavior, and higher homework completion (Alameda-Lawson, 2014). It is also interesting to note that parent trust was significantly associated with several dimensions of student behavior. It suggests that parent trust in their child's teacher and school may be an important point of intervention to improve student behavior concerns (Santiago, Garbacz, Beattie, & Moore, 2016).

In the study of Hughes and Kwok (2017), they found out that the quality of teachers' relationship with students and their parents mediates the association between children's background characteristics and teacher-rated classroom engagement, in turn, mediates the associations between student-teacher and parent-teacher relatedness and child achievement the following year (Hughes & Kwok, 2017). Such relationships allow the initial link between the background characteristics of children and their level of involvement in the classroom, as evaluated by teachers. Moreover, the research indicates that the level of participation in the school, as assessed by teachers, is influenced by these interactions. This, engagement, in turn acts as a mediator between the connections formed between students and teachers, as well as between parents and teachers, and the resulting academic accomplishment in the future academic year. This emphasizes the significance of cultivating robust teacher-student and teacher-parent connections for immediate classroom involvement and enduring academic achievements.

Hence, it is then established that building effective teacher-parent relationship is followed by the school improvement in terms of student performance. Development of effective relationship

between teachers and parents is affected by several factors including: (1) the degree of match between teachers' and parents' cultures and values, (2) societal forces at work on family and school, and (3) how teachers and parents view their roles (Reyes, n.d.).

Teacher-parent relations are significant as this allows flexible and effective parental involvement. Parental involvement refers to the amount of participation a parent has when it comes to the schooling of his/her children. Some schools foster healthy parental involvement, but sometimes parents has hesitations if they will involved themselves with their children's education (Bartolome, Mamat, & Masnan, 2017). Hence, in order establish a working relationship between the teachers and parents, strong communication is fundamental to this partnership and to building a sense of community between home and school. In these changing times, teachers must continue to develop and expand their skills in order to maximize effective communication with parents (Graham-Clay, n.d.).

The role of the teacher in a positive school community relationship is extremely important since it is the teacher who is the backbone of the educational system (Nebor, 2011). Hence, teachers should also be engaging in community involvement. In the study of Roxas, Viuya and Vallejo (2018) teachers who were involved in social activities, economic activities, cultural activities, political activities and religious activities claimed that they become productive and obtained positive interactions among the "multiplicity of personalities, cultures, beliefs and ideals" and "develop and teach students to learn through active participation in the community" (Roxas, Viuya, & Vallejo, 2018). Thus, they recommended that teachers should include in their annual/yearly plan of activities the possible community programs in which all the stakeholders will be involved.

In the Philippines, the Department of Education implements Brigada Eskwela where the school and community work together for school physical preparations for the opening of classes. This is most beneficial for the school. As pointed by Brook, Marek & Saulo (2014), a close cooperation and collaboration between schools and community is necessary to make the school serviceable and responsive to the need of the community whatever they may contribute in the school program effectively. When good relationships exist, the school reflects community life, and the community reflects the ideas of the school. Positive interactions between individuals contribute to a school environment that mirrors the dynamics of the surrounding community, while the community itself embodies the principles and values upheld by the school. Furthermore, these collaborative endeavors can be viewed as implementing transformation leadership principle., wherein leaders(school administrators) rally community resources and cultivate a collective vision. This collaborative methodology not only improves the physical surroundings of educational institutions but also fosters a robust sense of communal ownership and endorsement for educational endeavors, ultimately bolstering the comprehensive growth and adaptability of the educational system.

Belonging to professional associations and attending professional meetings has been promoted as an important aspect of career development. In joining professional organizations, one start joining and attending and presenting at conferences. This participation can facilitate networking, skill building, collaboration and mentoring. Consequently, conferences may contribute to increased professional development, collaboration, and advocacy, which can translate into more effective public health education programs and initiatives (Mata, Latham, & Ransome, 2017).

In addition, these connections at professional events frequently establish supportive peer networks. These networks can offer ongoing professional assistance, exchange of best practices, and promote a culture of continual learning and enhancement. Participating in such activities not only improves individual skills but also helps to advance the entire profession by fostering collaborative development and innovation.

3. Material and Methods

This study used a descriptive, quantitative, correlational, and causal research design. Research design serves as the blueprint for the researcher in answering the research question or testing the research hypothesis as it lays out the activities in conducting the study and how the researcher controls factors that may affect the validity of findings (Jongbo, 2014).

On the other hand, quantitative research design uses variables that are measurable to predict, explain, and control a phenomenon (Leedy, 1993). Moreover, the quantitative research method deals with quantifying and analyzing variables to get results. It involves the utilization and analysis of numerical data using specific statistical techniques to answer questions like who, how much, what, where, when, how many, and how (Apuke, 2017).

More specifically, this study utilized cross-sectional, descriptive, and correlational research design, specifically a survey. In a descriptive study, the researcher has no control of the variable at all. The task of the researcher is to explain the status quo of the group. A descriptive study, therefore, attempts to determine, describe, or identify the current situation of the population. Moreover, a correlational study is used when the researcher wants to study the extent of the relationship between two variables.

The respondents of this study were the 200 teachers of the identified Elementary and Secondary Schools in Compostela West District, Division of Davao de Oro. After establishing the sample size of 200, the stratified proportionate sampling technique was used to determine the samples of teachers from the identified 13 schools. The actual teacher-respondents from each school were selected through purposive sampling, where teachers with at least two years of teaching experience were considered. The years of teaching experience would warrant enough exposure to the transformational leadership style of their school heads or principals.

The school heads were considered for their demographic profile for data for age and gender as indicators for the moderating variable.

The researcher used the Transformational Leadership Scale of Balyer and Ozcon (2012). the questionnaire was designed for teachers to respond in evaluation the transformational leadership practices of school heads based on the following dimensions: vision building, individual consideration, intellectual stimulation and innovative climate. The scale was tested and found reliable. Cronbach alpha values found were 0.87 for vision building, 0.88 for individual consideration, 0.92 for intellectual consideration and 0.91 for the innovative climate sub-dimension. There are 24 items in the scale with the following distribution: 5 items for vision building, 6 items for individualized consideration, 7 items for intellectual stimulation and 6 items for innovative climate.

First part was to determine the demographics of the respondents for profiling purposes. Second part of the questionnaire is to determine the level of principals' transformational leadership with the following indicators or dimensions; vision building, individual consideration, intellectual stimulation, and innovative climate.

Moreover, to gauge the level of quality instruction of Junior High School teachers, scores of teachers in the IPCR-F in school years 2020-2021 and 2021-2022 will be used as measurement.

In order to determine the appropriateness of the transformational leadership scale of Balyer and Ozcon (2012) in the context of this study, a pilot test was conducted and Cronbach alpha was calculated using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS).

The instrument was adapted by the researcher in measuring the transformational leadership of school heads as perceived by the teachers. The instrument had undergone validity test by experts to mitigate the risk of forming incorrect hypothesis and ensure accuracy of results.

The instrument to be used are adopted hence item-validation was no longer be applicable. However, the questionnaire was subjected to face validation with the three experts.

Range of Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Meaning
4.5-5.0	Very High	This means that in general sense, school principals exhibit a range of associated practices that are always align to transformational leadership in achieving the desired school's goals and objectives.
3.5-4.49	High	This means that in general sense, school principals exhibit a range of associated practices that are nearly consistently align to transformational leadership in achieving the desired school's goals and objectives.
2.5-3.49	Moderate	This means that in general sense, school principals exhibit a range of associated practices that are usually align to transformational leadership in achieving the desired school's goals and objectives.
1.5-2.49	Low	This means that in general sense, school principals exhibit a range of associated practices that are sometimes align to transformational leadership in achieving the desired school's goals and objectives.
1.00-1.49	Very Low	This means that in general sense, school principals exhibit a very limited range of transformational leadership in achieving the desired school's goals and objectives.

The researcher meticulously adhered to prescribed protocols to obtain the requisite data for this study, guaranteeing the integrity of the conclusions in quantitative research. Before proceeding, authorization was acquired from the dean of the Graduate School and the director of Assumption College of Nabunturan. After receiving approval, a communication letter was dispatched to the Department of Education Davao de Oro Division to request permission and endorsement. This letter was then given to district supervisors to discuss the study's objectives and implementation.

Following the necessary authorizations from the school division Superintendent, District Supervisor, and School Principals, surveys were carried out among participants using printed and online platforms through Google Forms. Enumerators, who are grade heads employed for this purpose, delivered printed copies to instructors. To ensure the highest possible participation rate in the survey, we collected contact information and made individual efforts to reach out to those who still need to answer.

The enumerators provided teachers with instructions regarding the study's objective and responsibilities. The objectives, data use, and details regarding participation were made clear, and a user-friendly manual was provided alongside the questionnaire. Finished surveys were gathered one week later, and the data was discreetly analyzed using statistical analysis.

The ethics committee examined the strategy to verify compliance with ethical standards, considering consent procedures, confidentiality protocols, potential risks, research benefits, and researcher credentials. This comprehensive evaluation ensured the preservation of research

integrity and the maintenance of ethical principles, thereby cultivating trust among participants and the research community.

4. Results and Discussion

The results obtained from the collected data and the subsequent analysis and interpretation based on the problems presented. The findings explain significant trends and correlations related to the research questions. Detailed tables demonstrate the data trends. Moreover, the significance of these findings is examined in relation to the research collection.

4.1 Demographic Profile of Public Elementary and Secondary School Heads in West District of Compostela, Davao de Oro in terms of Sex and Age

Table 1

Demographic Profile of the Public Elementary and Secondary School Heads in West District Compostela, Davao de Oro in terms of Sex

SEX	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Male	7	54%
Female	6	46%
Total	13	100%

In the results presented in Table 1, male and female school heads have almost equal numbers. There were 7 Male School Heads comprising 54% of the total number of School Heads in the West District of Compostela, while there were 6 Female School Heads comprising 46%.

Table 2

Demographic Profile of the Public Elementary and Secondary School Heads in West District Compostela, Davao de Oro in terms of Age

LEVEL	AGE BRACKET	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1	40-49	3	23%
2	50-59	7	54%
3	60 and up	3	23%
		13	100%

From the results presented in Table 2, it can be seen that most of the School Heads in the West District of Compostela were from the age range of 50-59, where there are 7 out of 13 School Heads or 54% of the total number. Moreover, there were 3 school heads aged 40-49, and the same number of school heads who were aged 60 and up, both comprised 23% of the total number.

4.2 Level of Transformational Leadership

This section presents the results of the problem that examined the level of transformational leadership according to vision building, individualized consideration, intellectual stimulation, and innovative climate.

Table 3
 Level of Principal’s Transformational Leadership in terms of Vision Building

Indicator	Mean	Description
1. The school head/principal refers explicitly to our schools goals during decision-making processes	4.3	High
2. The school head/principal explains the relationship between the schools’ vision and initiatives of the school district, collaborative projects, or the government	4.4	High
3. The school head/principal discusses the consequences of the school’s vision for everyday practice	4.3	High
4. The school head/principal uses all possible moments to share the school’s vision with the team, the students, parents, and others	4.4	High
5. The school head/principal incorporate the school’s vision and goals for the future to talk about the current issues and problems facing the school	4.4	High
Overall Mean	4.4	High

It can be seen in table 3 that the overall mean is 4.4 which indicates that the level of transformational leadership in terms of vision building of school principal is high. This suggests that, on average, the principal’s performance across all indicators is rated high. This indicates that the principal is highly effective in aligning their actions and communications with the school’s goals and vision. Also, this means that in general sense, school principals exhibit a range of associated practices in vision building that are always align to transformational leadership in achieving the desired school’s goals and objectives. Teacher-respondents perceive that school principals excel in involving teachers in aligning school activities with the school’s vision and mission, as well as with the Department of Education’s (Deped) vision, mission, and targets. This suggest that principals effectively engage teachers in integrating these guiding principles into daily practices and strategic planning, ensuring cohesive efforts towards shared educational goals.

Results of this study suggest that the school principal effectively cascaded the school’s deliverables and targets to all stakeholders, including teachers, students, parents, and others. This shows that the school principals are exemplary in promoting transparency and collaborative efforts among its stakeholders by ensuring that stakeholders understood the school’s vision, mission, goals and performance targets. By keeping stakeholders informed and engaged, the principal fostered a notion that school’s success is a shared destiny of all stakeholders.

Table 4
 Level of Principal’s Transformational Leadership

in terms of Individualized Consideration

Indicator	Mean	Description
1. The school head/principal takes opinions of individual teachers seriously	4.4	High
2. The school head/principal listens carefully to team members' ideas and suggestions	4.3	High
3. The school head/principal is attentive to the problems that teachers encounter when implementing innovations	4.2	High
4. The school head/principal shows appreciation when a teacher takes initiative to improve the education	4.4	High
5. The school head/principal helps teachers talk about their feelings	4.3	High
Overall Mean	4.3	High

Table 4 shows that the two groups have the highest mean of 4.4, which indicates a high level. The two categories are "the school head/principal values the opinions of individual teachers" and "the school head/principal expresses gratitude when a teacher takes the initiative to enhance education." Following these categories are "the school head/principal demonstrates attentive listening to team members' ideas and suggestions" and "the school head/principal facilitates open discussions among teachers about their emotions," both of which have an average score of 4.3, indicating a high level of performance. The school principal has a high level of attentiveness towards the challenges faced by teachers in adopting innovations, as indicated by the lowest mean score of 4.2 with a descriptive equivalent of high level.

The results of this study indicate that school principals support teachers' personal and professional needs, which fosters a positive working environment. This makes teachers feel valued, motivated, and empowered to grow personally and professionally. This supportive atmosphere encourages teachers to perform their best, contributing to a more collaborative, motivated, and effective educational setting. Moreover, the study's results indicate that school principals successfully demonstrate a genuine concern for the well-being of their teachers, fostering an environment where they feel understood, supported, and respected.

Lastly, result are indicative that school principals are paying attention to teachers' concerns and issues in the class and in the school especially in implementing curricular activities. It shows that school principals actively listen to teachers' concerns and by doing so they gain understanding of different areas that need improvement for smoother implementation of school programs, projects, activities and initiatives. When school principals are being attentive to teachers' problem or challenges, this makes implementation of schools' projects, activities, programs and other innovations both in classroom and school level successful. It might be because when teachers feel supported and understood, they will likely show commitment and motivated engagement to implementation process.

Table 5

Level of Principal's Transformational Leadership in terms of Intellectual Stimulation

Indicator	Mean	Description
1. The school head/principal encourages to experiment with new didactic strategies	4.4	High
2. The school head/principal encourages teachers to try new strategies that match their personal interests.	4.4	High
3. The school head/principal helps teacher to reflect in new experiences	4.4	High
4. The school head/principal motivates teachers to look for and discuss new information and ideas that are relevant to the school's development	4.4	High
5. The school head/principal stimulates teachers to constantly think about how to improve the school	4.4	High
Overall Mean	4.4	High

The data presented in Table 5 demonstrates that all of the following categories are observed: "the school head/principal encourages experimentation with new teaching strategies," "the school head/principal encourages teachers to explore strategies that align with their personal interests," "the school head/principal supports teachers in reflecting on new experiences," "the school head/principal motivates teachers to seek and discuss new information and ideas that contribute to the school's growth," and "the school head/principal inspires teachers to continuously contemplate ways to enhance the school." Obtained a mean score of 4.4, which corresponds to a descriptive level of high. The consistently high scores in these categories emphasize the principal's influential role in fostering intellectual stimulation among teachers.

A high-level rating on this indicator also indicates the school principals' excellent effort in encouraging teachers to be more reflective in their new experiences. Reflection involves thoughtful examination and analysis of one's experiences hence self- assessment and evaluation are paramount. Following the logic, school principals promote reflective - environment school the practice of honest self-assessment and careful evaluation. This might be feasible if school principals provide resources to teachers to facilitate reflective activities. These include mentoring, feedback sessions, workshops, and the like.

The result of this study is incongruent to that of (Maniam et al., 2020). they concluded that teachers perceive the transformational leadership of their school principals in terms of intellectual stimulation as high. Asamoah, Puni, & Mohammad (2018) mentioned that leaders who act as intellectual stimulators in school encourage originality, experimentation, and creativity by soliciting ideas, opinions, and teacher feedback. These leaders promote problem-solving, alternative thinking, and critical thinking, fostering an environment of intellectual stimulation (Asamoah, Puni, & Mohammed, 2018). Hence, intellectual stimulation type of leadership positively and significantly impacted employees' job satisfaction (Haleem, Jehangir, & Rehman, 2018).

Table 6

Principal's Transformational Leadership in terms of Innovative Climate

Indicator	Mean	Description
1. Teachers are generally willing to try new ideas	4.6	Very High
2. Teachers are continuously learning and developing new ideas	4.6	Very High
3. Teachers have a positive “can-do” attitude	4.6	Very High
4. Teachers are willing to take risks to make this school better	4.5	Very High
5. Teachers are constantly trying to improve their teaching	4.6	Very high
Overall Mean	4.6	Very High

The results also indicate that the average score is 4.6, which is considered quite high. In essence, school administrators demonstrate the qualities of a transformational leader by effectively creating a school atmosphere that promotes innovation and encourages teachers to think creatively, experiment, and adopt new teaching methods and practices. The consistently high scores in multiple areas highlight the principal's efficacy in facilitating teachers' exploration of innovative approaches to teaching and learning.

The level of transformational leadership in terms of innovative climate is very high. The consistent very high rating across the categories under this indicator reflects the exemplary ability of the school principals in demonstrating a range of associated practices in promoting innovative climate in their stations or schools. These practices are always aligned to transformational leadership in achieving the desired school's goals and objectives.

4.3 Level of Performance of Teacher

Table 7

Performance of Teachers of Compostela West District

Indicator	Mean	Descriptive
Average Performance Rating of Teachers	4.4	Very Satisfactory

As stated in Table 7, teachers have an average performance rating of 4.4, which is considered extremely satisfactory. The high ranking of teachers' performance suggests that teachers in Compostela West District are proficient and productive in fulfilling their responsibilities and achieving their performance goals. This further demonstrates that the teachers' involvement in achieving school objectives is of utmost significance. The "very satisfactory" rating indicates a high level of performance, suggesting that teachers are displaying competence and dedication to achieving school objectives.

4.4 Difference in the Transformational Leadership Skills of School Heads

Table 8

**Significant Difference in the Transformational Leadership Skills of
 School Heads when Grouped according to Sex**

	t	df	p
PRINCIPALS’ TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADESHIP SKILLS	-1.536	11	0.153

The table displays a t-test value of -1.536, along with a degree of freedom (df) of 11. The obtained p-value of 0.153 exceeds the predetermined criterion of significance of 0.05 for this investigation. This suggests that there is not enough evidence to dismiss the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant disparity in the level of transformational leadership qualities among school administrators when respondents are categorized by gender. This indicates that any observed disparity in leadership abilities ratings between male and female respondents is more likely to be a result of random variation rather than an actual difference. Therefore, the gender of the participants does not seem to have a major impact on their evaluation of the principals' transformational leadership abilities.

Table 9

**Significant Difference in the Transformational Leadership Skills
 of School Heads when Grouped according to Age**

ANOVA - PRINCIPALS’ TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP SKILLS

Cases	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	p
AGE	0.059	2	0.029	0.149	0.863
Residuals	1.973	10	0.197		

The table shows that the calculated f-value is 0.149, with 2 degrees of freedom (df). This suggests that the study involves the comparison of three different age groups. The table displays a p-value of 0.863, which is above the accepted significance level of 0.05. This suggests that there is no statistically significant variation in the transformational leadership abilities of school principals when respondents are categorized based on their age group. Put simply, the variations in leadership ratings among different age groups of respondents can be attributed to mere chance.

4.5 Significant relationship between transformational leadership of school heads and teachers’ performance

Table 10

Correlation Results on Relationship between transformational leadership
of School Heads and Teachers' Performance

Pearson's Correlations

VARIABLE	P-VALUE	CORRELATION COEFFICIENT	REMARKS
Transformational Leadership Skills	0.621	0.035	Not significant
Individual Performance Commitment and Review			

The data table displays a Pearson's r-value of 0.035 and a p-value of 0.621. Pearson's correlation coefficient of 0.035 suggests a very small positive link between transformational leadership and teachers' performance. This implies that there is a minimal correlation between the qualities of transformational leadership and the performance of teachers. This demonstrates that the transformational leadership qualities of school principals do not have an impact on how teachers achieve their performance objectives.

5. Recommendations

The researcher of this study would like to propose the following recommendations:

1. The government, through the Department of Education and its school heads, sustains the practices aligned to the principles of transformational leadership practices in and out of the school and strengthens professional development programs that are aligned with the individual concerns of the teachers.
2. DepEd officials and teachers can establish school-based training and activities to enhance teachers' performance and sustain transformational leadership practices in the school. This can be done through SLAC and action research.
3. The future researcher may consider including additional factors to be included in their research about transformational leadership and teaching performance. The complexity of transformational leadership and the multi-faceted nature of teaching performance can be explored in future studies to obtain more comprehensive insights.

6. Conclusion

Based on the result of the study, teachers perceived that school principals are effectively and efficiently implement transformational leadership in their schools. Principals' associated practices such as vision building, individualized consideration, intellectual stimulation and innovative

climate are in line with the principles of transformational leadership. It is also found out that the teachers' performance is very satisfactory which means that they exceeded their targets and deliverables.

Moreover, this study found out that the view on the school principals' transformational leadership practices is uniform across all teachers in both sexes and age-groups. This indicates that school principals are objective and consistent in implementing their leadership styles and its associated practices. Lastly, this study concluded that there is no significant relationship between the perspective of teachers on school principal's transformational leadership and the teacher performance. This indicates that the way how teachers perceived the leadership style of the school principals has no effect on their teaching performance. This suggests that while transformational leadership are valued, its direct impact on teaching performance in this context is not evident. Other factors affecting teaching performance should be explored to understand their interplay with leadership dynamics.

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